

Collective Electron Oscillation in Pi-Electron System on Linear and Cyclic Polyenes : A Generator Coordinate Method

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The generator coordinate method has been applied to the study of collective motion of pi-electron system in linear and cyclic polyenes. This method has been found to be very useful since it can be applied to any number of particles in any potential field.

OF late the Tomonaga method for the study of collective motion of many body system has been applied to the case of pi-electron system of linear and cyclic polyenes with some interesting results.¹ There is another method, the so called generator coordinate method², which has been very successful in the study of collective motion of nuclear particles and which hold for any potential field and any number of particles in a monocentric field. Since the free electron wave functions of linear and cyclic polyenes are basically one center functions, it was surmised that the generator coordinate method may be applied to study the collective motions of the π -electrons in these systems also using FEMO. The present paper reports the result of such an investigation.

Generator coordinate method

We briefly review the generator coordinate method. Let us consider a system of N particles with coordinates x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N with a Hamiltonian function

$$H = \frac{p_1^2}{2m} + \frac{p_2^2}{2m} + \frac{p_N^2}{2m} + \sum V(r_{ij})$$

we replace the actual potential felt by a particle by a fictitious potential characterised by a shape parameter, α . We solve the wave equation for individual particles moving in this potential field. Out of these individual particle wave functions we construct by formation of a determinant a many particle wave function $Q_N(x_1, \dots, x_N, \alpha)$. This function is completely and uniquely determined once one knows the construction potential as a function of α .

The trial function for the many particle system is now taken to be given by

$$\psi(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \int Q(x_1, \dots, x_N, \alpha) f(\alpha) d\alpha.$$

Here the quantity, α , may be given the name of generator coordinate because it serves to generate the wave function of the system. It should be emphasised that this generator coordinate is not a function of the coordinates of the individual particles. The undetermined generator wave function $f(\alpha)$ is a function of α alone. Since $f(\alpha)$ does not depend on the particular coordinates, it must be a collective wave function of the many particle system.

We next determine this collective wave function by the requirement that the expectation value of the energy of the N-particle system should be an extremum with respect to generator wave function $f(\alpha)$, i.e.

$$\delta E = 0 \text{ or } \frac{\delta E}{\delta f(\alpha)} = 0$$

We shall now find the trial function that extremises the energy

$$E = \frac{\int \psi^*(x) H \psi(x) d\tau_1, \dots, d\tau_N}{\int \psi^*(x) \psi(x) d\tau_1, \dots, d\tau_N}$$

We substitute the trial functions

$$\psi^*(x) = \int Q^*(x, \alpha) f^*(\alpha) d\alpha$$

$$\psi(x) = \int Q(x, \beta) f(\beta) d\beta$$

In the energy expression all terms dependent on coordinates are known, hence the integration over them can be performed easily. Only integration with respect to α and β remains to be done.

$$E = \frac{\int f^*(\alpha) K(\alpha, \beta) f(\beta) d\alpha d\beta}{\int f^*(\alpha) I(\alpha, \beta) f(\beta) d\alpha d\beta}$$

where $\left\{ \begin{matrix} I(\alpha, \beta) \\ K(\alpha, \beta) \end{matrix} \right\} = \int Q^*(x_1 \dots x_N, \alpha) \left\{ \begin{matrix} I \\ H \end{matrix} \right\} Q(x_1 \dots x_N, \alpha) d\tau_1 \dots d\tau_N$

I and K are called respectively "overlap kernel" and "energy kernel".

By extremising the energy expression we get

$$0 = \delta E = \frac{\int d\alpha \delta f^*(\alpha) \int [K(\alpha, \beta) - EI(\alpha, \beta)] f(\beta) d\beta}{\int f^*(\alpha) I(\alpha, \beta) f(\beta) d\alpha d\beta}$$

+ complex conjugate.

The coefficients of $\delta f^*(\alpha)$ and $\delta f(\alpha)$ must vanish individually because these are two linearly independent variables. Thus we arrive at the generator wave equation.

$$\int [E(\alpha, \beta) - EI(\alpha, \beta)] f(\beta) d\beta = 0$$

and its complex conjugate. The wave equation for collective function thus happens to be an integral equation. In the next two sections we solve this equation for π -electron system in linear and cyclic polyenes.

Linear polyenes

Linear polyene molecules have long chain of conjugated double bonds. If we assume the π -electrons to be free, then we may consider a one dimensional motion of the electrons trapped in a potential well of length L, L being the length of the chain. If we neglect the interaction between the electrons then the eigen value and eigen functions are given as

$$\epsilon_{(n)} = \frac{h^2 n^2}{2Lm}, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots$$

$$U_n = \frac{1}{L} \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i}{L} n x\right)$$

where m is the electronic mass and x varies from $-L/2$ to $+L/2$. The ground state of the system

is such that the one electron levels are occupied by electrons in energy order from the lowest according to the Pauli Principle. We now introduce the interaction potential by a fictitious potential characterised by a shape parameter α , such that x now varies from $\alpha = 1/2 L$ to $\alpha + 1/2 L$ and the eigen functions are given by

$$U_n(x, \alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \exp\left[\frac{2\pi i n(x - \alpha)}{L}\right]$$

Let us consider a simple case with two electrons only. From Pauli Principle the two electrons should go to the same level (i.e. same n value) in the ground state. In this case the above formulation shows the energy E of the system will simply be the internal energy of the system and no collective motion could be obtained. This should be the case because for this method to work the wave function should be expressible as a Slater determinant. This is possible if the two electrons occupy levels with different n-values. Let us consider the case where two electrons occupy the levels with n=1 and n=2. The individual particle eigen functions will be

$$U_1(x_1, \alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \exp\left[\frac{2\pi i (x_1 - \alpha)}{L}\right]$$

$$U_2(x_2, \alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \exp\left[\frac{8\pi i (x_2 - \alpha)}{L}\right]$$

From these we construct the antisymmetrised two particle eigen function as

$$Q_1(x_1, x_2, \alpha) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{vmatrix} U_1(x_1, \alpha) & U_1(x_2, \alpha) \\ U_2(x_1, \alpha) & U_2(x_2, \alpha) \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2L}} \left[e^{\frac{2\pi i}{L} \left(\frac{2X + \alpha}{2}\right)} e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{L}(x - \alpha)} - e^{\frac{2\pi i}{L} \left(\frac{x + \alpha}{2}\right)} e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{L} \left(\frac{2x + \alpha}{2}\right)} \right]$$

where $X = \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2)$ and $x = x_2 - x_1$ i.e. m. X and x are just the center of mass coordinate.

Next step is the calculation of energy kernel and overlap kernel given by

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} I(\alpha, \beta) \\ K(\alpha, \beta) \end{matrix} \right\} = \iint Q(x_1, x_2, \alpha) \left\{ \begin{matrix} h^2 \\ 8\pi^2 m \end{matrix} \right\} (\nabla_1^2 + \nabla_2^2) Q(x_1, x_2, \beta) dx_1 dx_2$$

These integrals are easily calculated on the center of mass coordinate if we write the exponentials as sines and cosines, and then take the real part only. Thus we get

$$I(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\pi \cos \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \left\{ 2 \cos \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} + 1 \right\} + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sin \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \cos \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} - \sin \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \cos \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \right\} + \frac{1}{4} \cos \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \sin \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \right]$$

$$K(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{h^2}{64\pi^2 mL^2} \left[\frac{23}{4} \sin \frac{3\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} - \cos \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \sin \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} + \pi \left\{ 11 \cos \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} + 2 \cos \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \cos \frac{2\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \right\} - \frac{1}{4} \sin \frac{\pi(\alpha - \beta)}{L} \right]$$

The solution of generator equation for collective motion is greatly simplified in the present problem by the circumstances that the kernels $I(\alpha, \beta)$ and $K(\alpha, \beta)$ depend on the difference $\alpha - \beta$ but not on α and β individually. By well-known group theoretical arguments this leads one to expect the solution in the form

$$f(\beta) = \exp(ik\beta)$$

i.e., the collective motion is an oscillatory motion. The energy should have the value

$$E = \frac{\int K(O, \beta) \exp(ik\beta) d\beta}{\int I(O, \beta) \exp(ik\beta) d\beta} = \frac{h^2}{4mL^2} \left(\frac{8\pi^2 + (8\pi - kL) \sin kL}{5\pi^2 + (2kL - 10\pi) \sin kL} \right) + \frac{h^2 k^2}{16\pi^2 m}$$

for low frequency collective oscillations. The first term depends on L , the length of the chain and the second term depends only on k . We conclude that the first part gives the internal motion and the second the collective motion. The collective frequency will be independent of chain length, but the internal motion will depend on the collective frequency. The internal energy diminishes as the length of the chain increases and for infinitely long chain the total energy will be given by the collective energy only. Is this the reason for convergence limit found in the linear

polyenes, which has been attributed to plasma oscillation by Araki³? In that case the collective oscillation should be associated with long wave transition in these systems.

It may be argued that the analysis holds only for two electrons only. Since in a multielectron system half of the electrons will be paired off and since it is only the electrons having different n -values which are used in the construction of determinants, even for multielectron system the total energy will separate out into collective energy (independent of chain length) and internal energy. But the energy integral for the internal energy cannot be evaluated in a closed form.

Cyclic polyene

The π -electrons in a cyclic polyene are assumed to move in a circular orbit of radius R in an axial potential field⁴

$$V_z = \frac{1}{2} kz^2$$

$$V = \frac{h^2}{8\pi^2 m} \frac{1}{4R^2 \eta^2} \left\{ \left(\frac{R}{\rho} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\rho}{R} \right)^2 - 2 \right\}$$

where k and η are two parameters which are determined from experimental data. The one electron eigen function in such a system is given by

$$\psi_{n2\eta\rho^m}(Z\rho\phi) = N e^{-\frac{kz^2}{2}} H_n \left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{k}} \right) e^{-\frac{c\rho^2}{2}}$$

$$F_{n\eta}^m(\sqrt{c\rho}) e^{imQ}$$

$H(\sqrt{kz})$ being a Hermit polynomial and $F(\sqrt{c\rho})$ is also a polynomial given by

$$F(\sqrt{c\rho}) = (\sqrt{c\rho})^\lambda \sum_{\nu=0}^{n\rho} a_\nu (\sqrt{c\rho})^\nu$$

If we fix our attention to the radial potential alone and solve for the radial motion we get

$$\psi(\rho) = (\sqrt{c\rho})^l e^{-c\rho^2/2}$$

i.e., λ is replaced by $l=0, 2, 4$, etc. (omitting the normalization constant). For a two electron case

with one electron in level $l=0$ and the other in $l=2$, we introduce the construction potential

$$V(\rho, \alpha) = \frac{\hbar^2}{8\pi^2 m} \frac{1}{4R^2 \eta^2} \left\{ \frac{R^2}{(\rho - \alpha)^2} + \frac{(\rho - \alpha)^2}{R^2} - 2 \right\}$$

The quantity α is the generator coordinate. We determine the usual single particle eigen function in this potential and then construct the antisymmetrised two particle function

$$Q(\rho_1, \rho_2, \alpha) = c(\rho_2^2 - \rho_1^2) \exp \left\{ -\frac{c}{2} \left[(\rho_1 - \alpha)^2 + (\rho_2 - \alpha)^2 \right] \right\}$$

omitting the normalising constant. The overlap kernel and energy kernels are given as

$$I(\alpha, \beta) = \exp \left[-\frac{c}{2} (\beta - \alpha)^2 \right]$$

$$K(\alpha, \beta) = \left\{ \epsilon + \frac{c\hbar^2}{16\pi^2 m} [1 - c(\beta - \alpha)^2] \right\} \exp \left[-\frac{c}{2} (\beta - \alpha)^2 \right]$$

again using the center of mass coordinates $X = \frac{\rho_1 + \rho_2}{2}$

and $x = \rho_1 - \rho_2$. The quantity ϵ stands for the integral

$$\epsilon = 2 \left(\frac{c}{2} \right)^{3/2} \int x \exp \left(-\frac{cx^2}{4} \right) \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{4\pi^2 m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(\rho_2 - \rho_1) \right] x \exp \left(-\frac{cx^2}{4} \right) dx$$

Since $I(\alpha, \beta)$ and $K(\alpha, \beta)$ depend only on the difference $(\beta - \alpha)$ and not on α and β individually, the unknown function $f(\beta)$ may be taken in the form

$$f(\beta) = \exp(ik\beta)$$

The energy value is given as

$$E = \frac{\int K(0, \beta) \exp(ik\beta) d\beta}{\int I(0, \beta) \exp(ik\beta) d\beta}$$

$$= \epsilon + \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{16\pi^2 m}$$

i.e., the energy is again the sum of internal and collective energies. In this case the internal energy is completely independent of collective motion as it is independent of k . As the size of the ring increases, i.e., as R increases the internal energy diminishes and for an infinitely large ring the whole energy should be all collective oscillation. Since no convergence limit is found in the spectra of cyclic polyenes, the collective modes cannot be associated with long wave length transition as has been the case with linear polyenes.

Remarks on two methods

Some very vital difference appears in the description of collective motion of the π -electron system by Tomonaga method and the generator coordinate method. In the Tomonaga¹ method the collective eigen function is a Hermit function whereas in the generator coordinate method it is a plane wave function. Further Tomonaga method holds for perfectly free electron gas with the number of electrons N large enough to make $1/\sqrt{N}$ small compared to unity, while the generator coordinate method applies to any kind of potential field and with any number of particles. When, however, the number of particles becomes very large the overlap kernel and energy kernel in generator coordinate method may be approximated by a Gaussian function of generator coordinate². In that case the generator function will be given by Hermit function as is the case in Tomonaga method. Since collective coordinate in Tomonaga method is related to internal coordinate, the collective oscillation takes into account configurational interaction in single particle description¹. On the other hand since the generator coordinate, α , is not in any way related to the internal coordinate, no such correlation is possible in this method.

References

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